

Supplementary information: Influence of soil texture on the estimation of soil organic carbon using Sentinel-2 temporal mosaics at 34 European sites

Wetterlind, J.¹, Simmler, M.², Castaldi, F.³, Borůvka, L.⁴, Gabriel, J.L.⁵, Gomes, L.C.⁶, Khosravi, V.⁴, Kivrak, C.⁷, Koparan, M.H.⁷, Lázaro-López, A.⁵, Łopatka, A.⁸, Liebisch, F.⁹, Rodriguez, J.A.⁵, Savaş, A.Ö.⁷, Stenberg, B.¹, Tunçay, T.⁷, Vinci, I.¹⁰, Volungevičius, J.¹¹, Žydelis, R.¹¹, Vaudour, E.¹²

¹ Swedish University of Agricultural Science (SLU), Department of Soil and Environment, Skara, Sweden

² Agroscope, Sustainability Assessment and Agricultural Management, Ettenhausen, Switzerland

³ National Research Council of Italy (CNR) Institute of BioEconomy, Firenze, Italy

⁴ Czech University of Life Sciences Prague (CZU), Faculty of Agrobiological Sciences, Department of Soil Science and Soil Protection, Prague, Czech Republic

⁵ Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Tecnología Agraria y Alimentaria (INIA-CSIC), Madrid, Spain

⁶ Aarhus University (AU), Department of Agroecology, Tjele, Denmark

⁷ Republic of Turkey Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, General Directorate of Agricultural Research and Policies (TAGEM), Ankara, Türkiye

⁸ Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation – National Research Institute (IUNG), Puławy, Poland;

⁹ Agroscope, Agroecology and Environment, Zürich, Switzerland

¹⁰ Environmental Protection Agency of the Veneto Region (ARPAV), Italy

¹¹ Lithuanian Research Centre for Agriculture and Forestry (LAMMC), Institute of Agriculture, Kėdainiai, Lithuania

¹² Université Paris-Saclay, INRAE, AgroParisTech, UMR EcoSys, 91120 Palaiseau, France

Correspondence: Johanna Wetterlind. E-mail: johanna.wetterlind@slu.se

Supplementary section

Table S1-3 present an overview of the 34 sites included in the study, the soil sampling and soil analyses.

Figure S1 shows temporal mosaics based on the median and the R90 method at three example sites.

Table S4 presents the performance of site-specific random forest models for predicting SOC and clay as determined in leave-one-out cross-validation. Similar to Table 1 in the paper for the PLSR models.

Figure S2 shows the performance of the site-specific random forest models. Similar to Figure 5 in the paper for the PLSR models.

Figure S3 shows the relative importance of the satellite bands in the PLSR models for predicting SOC and clay content (same data as in Figure 8 in the paper).

Table S1. Site information, dominant soil type according to the WRB systems with one principal qualifier.

Site	Lat	Long	Soil type
SWE 1	58.4	13.43	<i>No information</i>
SWE 2	58.38	13.48	<i>No information</i>
SWE 3	58.38	13.3	<i>No information</i>
SWE 4	58.25	13.13	<i>No information</i>
SWE 5	58.26	13.13	<i>No information</i>
SWE 6	58.23	13.13	<i>No information</i>
DNK 1	56.93	8.65	Chernic Phaeozems
DNK 2	56.37	9.57	Haplic Umbrisols, Haplic Phaeozems, Histosols, Haplic Luvisols
DNK 3	55.49	9.07	Chernic Phaeozems
DNK 4	55.32	11.34	Chernic Phaeozems
DNK 5	54.89	9.12	Umbric Podzols
LTU 1	55.73	21.46	Glossic Retisols, Gleyic Luvisols
LTU 2	55.38	23.86	Gleyic Luvisols
LTU 3	55.25	24.85	Gleyic Luvisols, Eutric Planosols, Mollic Gleysols
LTU 4	54.75	24.78	Calcaric Luvisols
POL 1	51.47	22.05	Podzols
CZE 1	50.52	15.42	Eutric Cambisols
CZE 2	50.39	15.26	Haplic Luvisols, Albic Luvisols, Luvic Chernozems
CZE 3	50.08	14.9	Calcic Chernozems, Luvic Chernozems, Eutric Regosols
CZE 4	49.86	14.74	Haplic Stagnosols, Stagnic Cambisols, Eutric Leptosols
FRA 1	48.9	1.85	Haplic Luvisols, Calcaric Cambisols, Solimovic Cambisols
CHE 1	47.67	9.06	<i>No information</i>
CHE 2	47.58	8.79	<i>No information</i>
CHE 3	47.56	9.08	Dystric Gleysols, Haplic Alisols
CHE 4	47.45	8.68	<i>No information</i>
CHE 5	47.43	8.52	<i>No information</i>
ITA 1	45.86	12.5	Haplic Luvisols, Hypereutric Cambisols
ITA 2	45.6	12.49	Calcaric Gleysol, Gleyic Calcisol
ITA 3	45.4	12.17	Gleyic Calcisols, Calcic Gleysol
ITA 4	45.25	11.08	Gleyic Calcisols
ITA 5	45.17	11.49	Gleyic Calcisols
TUR 1	38.44	33.87	Calcaric Fluvisols, Haplic Vertisols
TUR 2	36.73	28.78	Calcaric Fluvisols
ESP 1	37.66	-0.86	Haplic Calcisols

Table S2. Site information, soil sampling. Area is calculated using a convex hull round the sampling points. Nr = number of sampling points.

Site	area (ha)	Nr	Density (samples /ha)	sampling design	based on	Sampling depth (cm)	Sample area (m ²)	Soil sampling year
SWE 1	259	83	1*	targeted sampling	satellite data	0-20	30	2015
SWE 2	56	51	1	targeted sampling	satellite data	0-20	30	2015
SWE 3	44	38	1	targeted sampling	satellite data	0-20	30	2010
SWE 4	1136	175	0.2	targeted sampling	soil property maps	0-20	30	2005
SWE 5	25	122	5	regular grid	-	0-20	30	2001
SWE 6	37	159	4	regular grid	-	0-20	30	2001
DNK 1	0.9	53	60	regular grid	-	0-20	20	2010
DNK 2	11	280	26	regular grid	-	0-20	20	1992
DNK 3	0.6	37	59	regular grid	-	0-20	20	2011
DNK 4	1.7	81	47	regular grid	-	0-20	20	2011
DNK 5	1.6	88	54	regular grid	-	0-20	20	2012
LTU 1	1.8	53	29	regular grid	-	0-20	1	2021
LTU 2	1.5	47	31	regular grid	-	0-20	1	2021
LTU 3	4.0	109	27	regular grid	-	0-20	1	2021
LTU 4	1.9	56	30	regular grid	-	0-20	1	2021
POL 1	101	32	0.3	transects	-			
CZE 1	300	78	0.6*	targeted sampling	soil map and satellite data	0-20	6.25	2021
CZE 2	565	76	0.5*	targeted sampling	soil map and satellite data	0-20	6.25	2021
CZE 3	631	80	0.5	targeted sampling	soil map and satellite data	0-20	6.25	2021
CZE 4	82	78	1	targeted sampling	soil map and satellite data	0-20 cm	6.25	2021
FRA 1	13	28	2	targeted sampling	soil map and satellite data	0-10 cm		2013 & 2015
CHE 1	0.7	22	33	regular grid	-	0-20 cm	0.25	2022
CHE 2	1.4	16	11	regular grid	-	0-20 cm	0.25	2022
CHE 3	2.8	35	13	regular grid	-	0-20 cm	0.25	2021
CHE 4	0.6	20	31	regular grid	-	0-20 cm	0.25	2022
CHE 5	0.8	20	25	regular grid	-	0-20 cm	0.25	2021
ITA 1	12	18	2	targeted sampling	soil map	0-30 cm	79	2018
ITA 2	12	18	2	targeted sampling	soil map	0-30 cm	79	2018
ITA 3	20	54	3	targeted sampling	soil map	0-30 cm	79	2018
ITA 4	20	54	3	targeted sampling	soil map	0-30 cm	79	2018
ITA 5	27	53	2	targeted sampling	soil map	0-30 cm	79	2018
TUR 1	477	120	0.3	evenly distributed	-	0-20 cm	4	2021
TUR 2	104	82	1	evenly distributed	-	0-20 cm	4	2021
ESP 1	114	50	1*	regular grid	-	0-10 cm	40	2022

* Sites with more than one field where the fields are not always next to one another. Sample density refers here to the density at the sampled fields.

Table S3. Site information, SOC and soil texture analyses methods

Site	SOC analysis method	soil texture analysis method
SWE 1	Loss on ignition corrected for structural water in clay minerals, multiplied by a factor 0.58	wetsieving and sedimentation (SS ISO 11277 2001)
SWE 2	Loss on ignition corrected for structural water in clay minerals, multiplied by a factor 0.58	wetsieving and sedimentation (SS ISO 11277 2001)
SWE 3	Loss on ignition corrected for structural water in clay minerals, multiplied by a factor 0.58	wetsieving and sedimentation (SS ISO 11277 2001)
SWE 4	Loss on ignition corrected for structural water in clay minerals, multiplied by a factor 0.58	wetsieving and sedimentation (SS ISO 11277 2001)
SWE 5	Loss on ignition corrected for structural water in clay minerals, multiplied by a factor 0.58	wetsieving and sedimentation (SS ISO 11277 2001)
SWE 6	Loss on ignition corrected for structural water in clay minerals, multiplied by a factor 0.58	wetsieving and sedimentation (SS ISO 11277 2001)
DNK 1	combustion in a LECO induction furnace	Pipette method (ISO 11277:2009)
DNK 2	combustion in a LECO induction furnace	Pipette method (ISO 11277:2009)
DNK 3	combustion in a LECO induction furnace	Pipette method (ISO 11277:2009)
DNK 4	combustion in a LECO induction furnace	Pipette method (ISO 11277:2009)
DNK 5	combustion in a LECO induction furnace	Pipette method (ISO 11277:2009)
LTU 1	SOC content was determined by photometric procedure at the wavelength of 590 nm using UV-VIS spectrophotometer Cary (Varian) and using glucose as a standard.	Pipette method (ISO 11277:2009)
LTU 2	SOC content was determined by photometric procedure at the wavelength of 590 nm using UV-VIS spectrophotometer Cary (Varian) and using glucose as a standard.	Pipette method (ISO 11277:2009)
LTU 3	SOC content was determined by photometric procedure at the wavelength of 590 nm using UV-VIS spectrophotometer Cary (Varian) and using glucose as a standard.	Pipette method (ISO 11277:2009)
LTU 4	SOC content was determined by photometric procedure at the wavelength of 590 nm using UV-VIS spectrophotometer Cary (Varian) and using glucose as a standard.	Pipette method (ISO 11277:2009)
POL 1	Modified Tiurin's method	Sedimentation, areometric Casagrande method (PN-ISO 11277)
CZE 1	Walkley-Black	Pipette method (ISO 11277:2009)
CZE 2	Walkley-Black	Pipette method (ISO 11277:2009)
CZE 3	Walkley-Black	Pipette method (ISO 11277:2009)
CZE 4	Walkley-Black	Pipette method (ISO 11277:2009)
FRA 1	dry combustion (NF ISO 10694)	pipette method (NF X31-107)
CHE 1	dry combustion (NF ISO 13 878)	Pipette method (NFX 31-107)
CHE 2	dry combustion (NF ISO 13 878)	Pipette method (NFX 31-107)
CHE 3	dry combustion (NF ISO 13 878)	Pipette method (NFX 31-107)
CHE 4	dry combustion (NF ISO 13 878)	Pipette method (NFX 31-107)
CHE 5	dry combustion (NF ISO 13 878)	Pipette method (NFX 31-107)
ITA 1	EN 17505:2023 Dry combustion by thermal gradient (Temperature dependent differentiation of total carbon)	ISO 11277:2020
ITA 2	EN 17505:2023 Dry combustion by thermal gradient (Temperature dependent differentiation of total carbon)	ISO 11277:2020
ITA 3	EN 17505:2023 Dry combustion by thermal gradient (Temperature dependent differentiation of total carbon)	ISO 11277:2020
ITA 4	EN 17505:2023 Dry combustion by thermal gradient (Temperature dependent differentiation of total carbon)	ISO 11277:2020
ITA 5	EN 17505:2023 Dry combustion by thermal gradient (Temperature dependent differentiation of total carbon)	ISO 11277:2020
TUR 1	Walkley-Black	hydrometer method
TUR 2	Walkley-Black	hydrometer method
ESP 1	Walkley-Black	wetsieving and sedimentation (SS ISO 11277 2001)

Figure S1. Temporal mosaics shown as RGB images (B4, B3 and B2) of the median and the R90 approach at **A)** the Polish site POL 1, **B)** the French site FRA 1, and **C)** the Spanish site ESP 1.

Table S4. Performance of site-specific random forest models for predicting SOC and clay as determined in leave-one-out cross-validation. Predictors in the models for SOC include either satellite data only, satellite data and texture information, or texture information only. The best models (smallest RMSE) using either the median or R90 satellite data, as well as using either clay only or information on all three particle size fractions (clay, silt, sand; 'allTex') are listed.

Site	SOC predictions												Clay predictions								
	Satellite				Satellite + texture				Texture				Satellite								
	RMSE	RPD	RPIQ	ccc	RMSE	RPD	RPIQ	ccc	RMSE	RPD	RPIQ	ccc	RMSE	RPD	RPIQ	ccc					
SWE 1	R90	0.58	1.82	1.23	0.81	R90	clay	0.60	1.78	1.20	0.80	clay	1.17	0.91	0.62	0.05	med	4.04	1.31	1.98	0.60
SWE 2	med	0.46	1.00	1.40	0.23	med	allTex	0.42	1.09	1.53	0.38	allTex	0.45	1.01	1.41	0.39	R90	2.63	1.37	1.90	0.65
SWE 3	med	0.29	0.90	1.00	-0.03	med	allTex	0.29	0.92	1.02	-0.02	allTex	0.27	0.97	1.07	0.10	med	5.07	2.72	5.03	0.93
SWE 4	med	0.36	1.10	1.46	0.39	med	allTex	0.31	1.25	1.67	0.53	clay	0.40	0.98	1.31	0.18	med	6.14	1.75	2.60	0.80
SWE 5	med	0.48	1.16	1.30	0.50	med	clay	0.36	1.52	1.71	0.73	clay	0.42	1.33	1.50	0.64	med	2.88	2.42	1.30	0.91
SWE 6	med	0.35	1.52	1.82	0.72	med	clay	0.31	1.74	2.09	0.80	clay	0.42	1.26	1.51	0.59	med	4.70	1.40	1.38	0.67
DNK 1	med	0.07	1.54	1.94	0.73	med	clay	0.07	1.55	1.96	0.74	clay	0.11	0.98	1.23	0.32	med	0.85	1.60	2.77	0.76
DNK 2	R90	1.09	1.58	0.22	0.75	med	clay	0.91	1.89	0.26	0.84	allTex	1.69	1.02	0.14	0.24	med	1.23	1.41	2.18	0.67
DNK 3	med	0.57	2.87	2.64	0.93	med	clay	0.56	2.91	2.68	0.93	allTex	1.64	0.99	0.91	0.28	R90	1.52	1.12	1.24	0.37
DNK 4	R90	0.11	1.19	1.64	0.48	R90	allTex	0.11	1.18	1.63	0.46	clay	0.12	1.06	1.47	0.43	med	1.47	0.94	1.00	0.00
DNK 5	R90	0.18	1.20	1.58	0.52	R90	clay	0.16	1.29	1.71	0.60	clay	0.21	1.02	1.34	0.40	R90	0.32	1.25	1.62	0.56
LTU 1	med	0.19	1.19	1.59	0.52	med	allTex	0.17	1.33	1.77	0.61	allTex	0.19	1.21	1.61	0.54	R90	2.01	1.09	1.64	0.33
LTU 2	med	0.21	0.99	1.21	0.17	med	allTex	0.21	0.95	1.17	0.17	allTex	0.23	0.87	1.07	0.00	med	2.31	0.90	0.97	-0.03
LTU 3	med	0.43	1.13	1.00	0.41	med	allTex	0.41	1.19	1.06	0.54	allTex	0.42	1.17	1.04	0.54	med	2.85	1.01	1.51	0.16
LTU 4	med	0.25	0.97	1.23	0.11	R90	clay	0.19	1.27	1.61	0.57	clay	0.20	1.17	1.48	0.60	R90	3.23	1.06	1.76	0.34
POL 1	med	0.24	1.26	1.17	0.57	med	clay	0.22	1.41	1.30	0.64	allTex	0.25	1.21	1.12	0.53	med	1.95	1.06	0.95	0.25
CZE 1	R90	0.46	0.91	0.83	0.22	R90	allTex	0.45	0.91	0.84	0.23	clay	0.47	0.88	0.81	0.13	R90	4.46	0.90	1.26	-0.12
CZE 2	R90	0.19	1.20	1.52	0.56	med	allTex	0.18	1.30	1.64	0.63	allTex	0.22	1.08	1.37	0.42	med	2.58	1.83	2.20	0.82
CZE 3	R90	0.16	1.20	1.81	0.52	R90	clay	0.17	1.15	1.75	0.48	allTex	0.20	1.00	1.51	0.22	R90	3.65	1.14	0.88	0.45
CZE 4	R90	0.29	1.01	1.11	0.21	R90	allTex	0.29	1.02	1.12	0.21	clay	0.33	0.90	0.98	0.11	R90	4.01	0.92	1.00	0.04
FRA 1	med	0.26	1.26	1.53	0.60	med	clay	0.26	1.27	1.54	0.60	clay	0.29	1.16	1.41	0.57	med	1.70	2.41	4.63	0.90
CHE 1	med	0.12	1.27	2.13	0.60	R90	allTex	0.09	1.63	2.72	0.77	allTex	0.10	1.46	2.44	0.73	R90	2.24	1.43	2.36	0.71
CHE 2	med	0.10	1.57	2.13	0.70	med	clay	0.10	1.60	2.17	0.73	allTex	0.12	1.37	1.86	0.65	med	1.99	1.67	2.21	0.76
CHE 3	R90	0.26	1.04	1.49	0.33	R90	allTex	0.23	1.15	1.65	0.43	allTex	0.23	1.16	1.66	0.49	med	2.81	1.03	1.21	0.27
CHE 4	med	0.33	1.80	1.17	0.81	R90	clay	0.24	2.44	1.60	0.90	clay	0.27	2.19	1.43	0.89	med	2.66	1.89	2.40	0.83
CHE 5	R90	0.27	1.49	0.89	0.66	R90	clay	0.24	1.67	1.00	0.73	clay	0.22	1.88	1.12	0.80	R90	1.86	1.56	1.11	0.71
ITA 1	R90	0.13	0.96	1.43	0.22	med	clay	0.13	1.00	1.49	0.19	clay	0.14	0.93	1.39	0.30	R90	3.39	1.29	1.44	0.63
ITA 2	R90	0.09	1.17	1.48	0.44	R90	clay	0.09	1.18	1.49	0.43	clay	0.10	1.12	1.41	0.41	med	3.41	1.17	1.23	0.45
ITA 3	med	0.18	1.32	1.86	0.64	med	clay	0.16	1.48	2.08	0.70	allTex	0.20	1.18	1.66	0.56	R90	4.37	1.60	2.17	0.76
ITA 4	R90	0.06	1.04	1.53	0.29	R90	clay	0.06	1.06	1.55	0.29	allTex	0.08	0.87	1.27	-0.05	R90	1.64	1.06	1.51	0.24
ITA 5	med	0.18	1.09	1.42	0.40	med	clay	0.18	1.11	1.44	0.41	allTex	0.21	0.95	1.24	0.19	med	3.47	1.74	2.04	0.81
TUR 1	R90	0.24	0.94	1.25	0.05	R90	allTex	0.21	1.05	1.39	0.28	allTex	0.24	0.93	1.24	0.19	med	6.15	1.74	2.55	0.81
TUR 2	R90	0.14	1.33	1.90	0.66	med	clay	0.11	1.70	2.43	0.79	allTex	0.13	1.42	2.04	0.69	R90	6.15	1.33	1.53	0.65
ESP 1	med	0.12	1.40	1.52	0.67	med	allTex	0.11	1.45	1.57	0.66	allTex	0.17	0.97	1.05	0.23	R90	4.48	1.44	1.73	0.68
Median		0.24	1.19	1.47	0.52			0.21	1.28	1.58	0.60		0.22	1.04	1.36	0.41		2.83	1.35	1.63	0.65
Mean		0.28	1.28	1.45	0.48			0.25	1.40	1.58	0.55		0.35	1.14	1.32	0.39		3.07	1.43	1.86	0.54

Figure S2. A) Performance of site-specific random forest models for predicting SOC from satellite data. **B)** Performance of site-specific random forest models for predicting clay from satellite data. RPD and ccc were determined in leave-one-out cross-validation. The results are shown for the best models (smallest RMSE) using either the median or R90 satellite data (corresponding to Table S4). The dotted lines indicate the performance of the dummy models, which are simple baseline models, always predicting the mean of the measured SOC or clay content in the training data (ignoring the satellite information). The solid lines are only eye-guides. The order of sites (x-axis) corresponds to Figures 3 A, 3B, 4 A, and 5 in the paper.

Figure S3. Relative importance of predictors in the PLSR models for predicting SOC and clay from satellite data (median or R90, whichever resulted in the smallest RMSE for each site). **A)** For models predicting SOC. **B)** For models predicting clay content. **C)** The difference between the relative importances for models predicting SOC and for models predicting clay content (difference of data shown in panel A and B). Sites are sorted from top to bottom according to decreasing prediction performance (ccc) of the SOC models. The dendrogram shows the redundancy structure of the set of predictors. It is based on a (complete-linkage) hierarchical clustering of the median satellite dataset with distance between the bands defines as $1 - |r|$ (Pearson).